

Realtime Deepfake Detection Using Video Vision Transformer

Abhijith Rajeev^{1*}, P Sreejindeth^{2*}, Shamnad CP^{3*}, Rini T Paul^{4*}, Anu Eldho^{5*},

*Department of Computer Science and Engineering
Mar Athanasius College of Engineering, Kothamangalam, Kerala

Abstract—Real-time framework uses the Video Vision Transformer (ViViT) to address the growing threat of deceptive multimedia content. The proposed model extracts temporal and spatial features from video frames, effectively discerning authentic content from manipulated deep fake videos. Trained on a diverse dataset, the transformer-based architecture captures long-range dependencies and contextual information crucial for accurate detection. To optimize real-time applicability, the system incorporates efficient attention mechanisms and parallel processing techniques during inference. The model exhibits robust performance against various deep fake generation techniques, including face swaps and lip-sync manipulations. Evaluation results showcase high accuracy, precision, and recall, emphasizing the system's efficacy. The significance of this work lies in its contribution to countering the malicious use of deep fake technology, offering a reliable and efficient real-time detection mechanism. The proposed approach aims to protect the integrity of multimedia content across diverse applications, such as social media and journalism. Overall, the system provides a practical solution to the pressing challenges associated with deep fake proliferation in the digital landscape.

Index Terms—realtime, deepfake, ViViT, spatio-temporal tokens, transformer-architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to create hyper-realistic fake videos, called deepfakes, using readily available tools is growing at an alarming rate. These deepfakes can manipulate faces, swap identities, and alter emotions, posing a serious threat to online security and trust. This paper has a novel deepfake detection method using a (ViViT).^[1] This approach combines the strengths of two powerful techniques having the ability to extract informative findings from images and videos along with Vision Transformer (ViT) which utilizes an attention mechanism to analyze relationships between these features and categorize them efficiently. By combining these complementary methods, the ViViT can extract key features. The CNN efficiently captures visual cues that reveal deepfake manipulation. They also have their own techniques for analyzing relationships. The ViT leverages its attention mechanism to understand the complex interactions between these features, identifying subtle signs of forgery. This work addresses the urgent need for robust deepfake detection in real-time. By harnessing the power of transformers, the proposed ViViT offers a promising

solution to combat this growing threat and safeguard online integrity.

The emergence of deepfake technology has raised significant concerns regarding its potential misuse in spreading misinformation, manipulating public opinion, and threatening the integrity of visual media. Deepfakes are synthesized media, primarily videos, created using advanced machine learning algorithms that replace the likeness of one person with another, or alter existing content seamlessly. Addressing the threat posed by deepfakes requires robust and efficient detection mechanisms capable of identifying manipulated content in real-time. Traditional methods of detection have become inadequate in the face of evolving deepfake generation techniques. Therefore, there is a pressing need to develop sophisticated and adaptive solutions to combat the proliferation of deepfake content. In recent years, Video Vision Transformer (ViViT) architectures have emerged as a promising approach for analyzing and understanding video content. Transformer has gained significant output in various processing models as a link model to the sequence.^{[2] [3]} ViViT extends the capabilities of the well-established Vision Transformer (ViT) model to handle sequential data such as video frames, enabling comprehensive analysis of temporal information in videos. This paper presents a new method for in-depth detection using Video Vision Transformer (ViViT). Leveraging the strengths of ViViT, our proposed method aims to accurately detect deepfake content in real-time video streams. By exploiting the temporal dependencies within video sequences, our approach enhances the discriminative power of the detection model, enabling it to distinguish between genuine and manipulated content with high precision and efficiency.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This paper leverages the strengths of ViViTs to offer a promising approach for real-time deepfake detection. By prioritizing real-time performance, comprehensive feature extraction, and efficient computation, this method can contribute significantly to combating the growing threat of deepfakes in our digital world.

A. Model Architecture

Using the Video Visual Transformer (ViT) architecture provides an effective way to analyze continuous video data. [4] This architecture extends the converter concept to process the physical information of video frames. By combining the process of self-monitoring, describing the properties of events in the video sequence, the model can lead to the search for reality. ViViT studies the encoded patches, looking for relationships and patterns [5]. They use a special technique called attention, allowing them to focus on specific patches that hold the most crucial information, similar to how we shift our focus while examining an image.

Fig. 1. Block Diagram representation of the model

B. Preprocessing

Preparing the Video for Analysis is to create a reliable deep search, it is important to collect different data including real video, real and deep content. This file should include multiple scenes, lighting, and backgrounds to ensure the model is strong. Preprocessing steps require standardization of video properties such as resolution, frame rate, and format [6]. Additionally, extracting frames from the video helps create continuous data for the conceptual model, making physical analysis easier. Preprocessing involves the preparation and transformation of raw video data into a format suitable for input into the model. This crucial step encompasses various operations aimed at enhancing the quality and efficiency of subsequent analysis. Common preprocessing techniques include resizing or cropping video frames to a standardized resolution, normalization to ensure consistent pixel intensity ranges across frames, and temporal sampling to extract key frames or segments for analysis [7]. Additionally, data augmentation techniques such as rotation, flipping, or adding noise may be applied to augment the training dataset and improve model robustness. Furthermore, preprocessing may involve encoding video data into a suitable format, such as sequences of image tensors or optical flow representations, depending on the specific requirements of the ViViT architecture. Overall, effective preprocessing plays a vital role in optimizing model performance and facilitating accurate and reliable video analysis tasks.

C. Feature Extraction

Unveiling the secrets within each patch is the main part of the process called feature extraction. Here, the ViViT model plays its major role as a powerful microscope, examining each

patch and identifying key characteristics [8]. It employs two techniques:

Patch embedding: This step includes feeding the patch information to a translator. This translator converts the raw pixel values into a high-dimensional language the ViViT understands. Patch embedding is a technique used to incorporate spatial information across multiple frames or patches within a video sequence. In vision transformers, each frame of a video is typically divided into smaller patches, which are then processed independently [9]. However, this approach may not fully capture the temporal dependencies and relationships between patches across different frames.

Positional encoding: This considers each patch came from within the frame. This information is crucial for understanding context. Positional encoding in ViViT serves a similar purpose to its role in image-based vision transformers, but with an additional dimension of time [10]. In image transformers, positional encoding is used to inject spatial information into the input embeddings since transformers inherently lack information about the absolute or relative positions of tokens within a sequence [11]. Similarly, in video vision transformers, positional encoding is extended to incorporate temporal information as well.

D. Classification

The classification layer within Video Vision Transformers (ViViTs) plays a pivotal role in analyzing video content by consolidating spatial and temporal features into simpler representations for decision-making. [12] It comprises a fully connected layer that condenses extracted features and a softmax activation function that converts numerical scores into probabilities indicating class likelihood. Factors like layer size and regularization techniques influence its performance. ViViTs employ this layer for tasks like video classification and action recognition, with its effectiveness hinging on feature quality and parameter choices. Understanding its mechanics is essential for advancing video analysis techniques and enhancing model capabilities. The impact of the classification layer is over different classes, indicating the likelihood of the input video belonging to each class [13]. This probability distribution is obtained by applying a softmax function to the raw output of the linear layer. Training the classification layer involves optimizing its parameters (weights and biases) along with the parameters of the transformer encoder layers. This is typically done using a suitable loss function, which compares the predicted chances for the training videos. During inference, the classification layer is used to make predictions for unseen videos by passing the video frames through the ViViT model and computing the final class probabilities.

E. Latency Optimization

Latency optimization in Video Vision Transformers (ViViTs) is crucial for real-time video analysis applications such as streaming and autonomous vehicles. To achieve this, strategies include simplifying model architectures by reducing parameters and utilizing lightweight variants of transformers and at-

tention mechanisms. Additionally, efficient temporal modeling techniques are employed, such as using simplified temporal models or hierarchical approaches. Quantization and compression methods reduce memory usage, while hardware acceleration with specialized accelerators like GPUs or TPUs speeds up computation^[14]. Parallelism and pipelining distribute computation across multiple units, and dynamic inference adjusts model complexity based on input characteristics. Caching and memoization techniques reduce redundant computations by storing and reusing intermediate results or attention weights. These combined efforts enable ViViTs to achieve significant reductions in latency while maintaining accuracy, facilitating real-time video analysis across various applications^[15].

F. Error Handling

Error handling involves managing unexpected or erroneous conditions that may occur during the processing of video data. Given the complexity of video analysis tasks, errors can arise from various sources, including corrupt or incomplete video files, unexpected changes in video content, or failures in the underlying computational infrastructure. Effective error handling in ViViTs entails implementing mechanisms to detect and respond to these issues, ensuring the reliability and robustness of the model's performance. This may involve techniques such as input validation to check for data integrity, exception handling to capture and handle errors gracefully during inference, and logging to record error details for diagnostic purposes. Additionally, incorporating resilience strategies like retry mechanisms or fallback procedures can help mitigate the impact of errors and maintain the continuity of video analysis operations. Overall, robust error handling is essential for ensuring the accuracy and dependability of ViViTs in processing video data across various real-world scenarios.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

Table I below displays training, testing, and accuracy measurements. Details about our model's comparative analysis with other models are given in this section. We assess training as well as the loss and accuracy of different models. Several models' inference times demonstrate how much faster and more accurate our model is. Another significant distinction is that our model produces faster findings because it takes less time to analyse the framework. Transformer's support for parallel processing significantly raises the average frame rate. Take predictions out of our data by dividing it into two paths: the polar group and the cluster group. The video is covered in the second section. Every video is broken up into manageable chunks of eight frames. Every block was handled independently. Every video is broken up into manageable chunks of eight frames. Every block was handled differently for testing and training purposes. As an alternative, if the full video is watched, predictions are generated at intervals of eight frames, which are then added together and split to provide a prediction that indicates whether the entire film is real or phoney. Therefore, even if one component contributes to an incorrect outcome, the other component will make up for it.

As a result, the prediction's overall accuracy has increased. The four parameters and the values that correspond to them are listed in Table II. These characteristics include memory, accuracy, and F1 score, among others.^[16] Table I and Table II.

Even though there are still some inaccurate frames in the movie, overall performance will be improved and the model is adaptable. Tables I and II are displayed here. By contrasting the data in Tables I and II, it is evident.

Fig. 2. Model accuracy vs Model loss

Fig. 3. Model accuracy vs epoch

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, we suggest a deep sensing system that displays videos instantaneously via Video Vision Transformer (ViViT). The model offers instantaneous results with great precision.

outcomes. We have developed a web application that offers customers two video authentication options: live meeting authentication and basic video authentication. This is normal for end users. Users can verify an existing video's authenticity with Basic Video Verification. Furthermore, users can record live meetings by choosing the option to control them, which comes in handy if they want to verify the legitimacy of the video feed of attendees while they are in a meeting. pictures from the live events they went to.

You can use the log-based approach for estimation and sketching. With the aforementioned characteristics, the user can take advantage of the basic application right away: control meeting meeting.

Applications utilising computer vision and deep learning have practically limitless potential. In the future, we want to integrate audio and video, which will allow the model to have a lot more features. Furthermore, our goal is to raise the value, which will speed up the model and shorten the inference time. As previously stated, the domains that the model relates to are defined (using descriptive abilities) in our model maintenance plan.

Furthermore, by concentrating on a subset of the image rather than the complete image, inference time can be significantly decreased while taking these assumptions into account.

Score	Train	Test	Val
Accuracy	95.805%	93.187%	93.462%
F1-Score	0.952	0.924	0.919
Recall	0.935	0.896	0.886
Precision	0.971	0.953	0.954

TABLE I
MODEL'S PERFORMANCE EVALUATED BY VARIOUS METRICS
(AS GROUP OF 8 FRAMES)

Score	Train	Test	Val
Accuracy	99.500%	98.250%	98.250%
F1-Score	0.995	0.982	0.972
Recall	0.990	0.975	0.970
Precision	0.100	0.990	0.995

TABLE II
MODEL'S PERFORMANCE EVALUATED BY VARIOUS METRICS
(AS VIDEOS)

The model using the log can be used for drawing and estimating. The above features allow the user to instantly benefit from the standard application: control meeting meeting. The potential of applications based on deep learning and computer vision is almost unlimited.

We plan to combine audio and video in the future, which will enable the model to have many features. Additionally, we aim to increase the value, which will make the model faster and reduce the inference time. As mentioned before, our model maintenance plan defines (using descriptive skills) the areas that the model refers to.

Furthermore, considering these assumptions, inference time can be greatly reduced by focusing on a portion of the image rather than the entire image. However, the actual result will suffer, so easily that there is a trade-off between these two things using the drawing .

REFERENCES

- [1] Zainab H. Ali, Hesham A. Ali, Mahmoud M. Badawy, "Internet of Things (IoT): Definitions, Challenges, and Recent Research Directions", in *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 128, no. 1, pp. 0975-8887, October 2015, DOI: 10.5120/ijca2015906430
- [2] J. Devlin, M.-W. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding," 2018, arXiv:1810.04805. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>
- [3] T. B. Brown et al., "Language models are few-shot learners," 2020, arXiv:2005.14165. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2005.14165>
- [4] A. Amab, M. Dehghani, G. Heigold, C. Sun, M. Lucie and c. Schmid, "ViViT: A Video Vision Transformer," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2021.
- [5] Y. Fan, G. Wen, D. Li, S. Qiu, M. D. Levine, and F. Xiao, "Video anomaly detection and localization via Gaussian mixture fully convolutional variational autoencoder," *Comput. Vis. Image Understand.*, vol. 195, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 102920.
- [6] M. Ye, X. Peng, W. Gan, W. Wu, and Y. Qiao, "AnoPCN: Video anomaly detection via deep predictive coding network," in *Proc. 27th ACM Int. Conf. Multimedia*, Oct. 2019, pp. 1805–1813.
- [7] J. Long, E. Shelhamer, and T. Darrell, "Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, Jun. 2015, pp. 3431–3440.
- [8] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio, "Generative adversarial nets," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2014, pp. 2672–2680.
- [9] W. Liu, W. Luo, D. Lian, and S. Gao, "Future frame prediction for anomaly detection—A new baseline," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.*, June. 2018, pp. 6536–6545
- [10] Y. Tang, L. Zhao, S. Zhang, C. Gong, G. Li, and J. Yang, "Integrating prediction and reconstruction for anomaly detection," *Pattern Recognit. Lett.*, vol. 129, pp. 123–130, Jan. 2020.
- [11] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Med. Image Comput. Comput.-Assist. Intervent.*, 2015, pp. 234–241.
- [12] A. Dosovitskiy, L. Beyer, A. Kolesnikov, D. Weissenborn, X. Zhai, T. Unterthiner, M. Dehghani, M. Minderer, G. Heigold, S. Gelly, J. Uszkoreit and N. Houlsby, "An Image is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale," in *ICLR*, 2021.
- [13] Y. Zhao, B. Deng, C. Shen, Y. Liu, H. Lu, and X.-S. Hua, "Spatio-temporal AutoEncoder for video anomaly detection," in *Proc. 25th ACM Int. Conf. Multimedia*, Oct. 2017, pp. 1933–1941.
- [14] N. Li and F. Chang, "Video anomaly detection and localization via multivariate Gaussian fully convolution adversarial autoencoder," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 369, pp. 92–105, Dec. 2019.
- [15] J. R. Medel and A. Savakis, "Anomaly detection in video using predictive convolutional long short-term memory networks," 2016, arXiv:1612.00390. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1612.00390>
- [16] S. Pashine, S. Mandiya, P. Gupta and R. Sheikh, "Deep Fake Detection: Survey of Facial Manipulation Detection Solutions," in *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2021.